

Hybrid Self-Reconfigurable Platform for Inspection: The Crawler Unit

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Abstract—Relieving humans from repetitive or dangerous tasks such as inspection and maintenance is one of the main goal of robotics. However, inspection robots have low fault tolerance and modest adaptability to different tasks. In such perspective, self-reconfigurable robots have proven superior performance. Here, the main components of a novel modular, self-reconfigurable hybrid platform for inspection are discussed. In particular, this work focuses on the crawler unit of such platform. The vehicle shows good ground maneuverability over different kind of terrains. Thanks to its design, the crawler can overcome ditches, climb ramps, move over uneven terrain and turn corners. Through the docking module, the vehicle can reconfigure into a snake robot coupling with its twin unit or into an arm when connected to the main base.

Index Terms—Hybrid self-reconfigurable system, Modular robot, Inspection robot

I. INTRODUCTION

In industrial plants and civil infrastructures, inspection and maintenance are crucial, since unexpected failures may produce catastrophic events. Nowadays, inspections are mainly performed by humans. Usually, operations involve data collection and visual assessment about target conditions. Nonetheless, even regular inspections may pose serious threats to workers, especially in confined spaces. In plant and pipe inspection, robots are assuming particular relevance. In these contexts, inspection operations are often analogous and present many similar challenges: harsh environment, obstacles, small entrances, etc. Many common features can be identified in the designs of such inspection systems. Robots for inspection of specific equipment are highly specialized devices such as the ones described in [1], [2]. Usually, these robots exhibit a small-sized and target-oriented design, which confer them superior performance, but reduce their versatility. During general inspections, robots have to collect data on wide areas, therefore such systems consist in mobile platforms equipped with sensors and robotic arms [3], [4]. Wheeled or tracked platforms are very big for moving fast. Narrow spaces, slopes, obstacles and stairs are still open challenges for such devices. Likewise, pipe inspection robots have to traverse long distances, but in constrained environment. For locomotion, mainly wheels or tracks are used, [5], [6]. However, pipelines result from the combination of many segments, therefore snake robots are more appropriate, see [7]–[9]. Self-reconfigurability is an interesting trade-off for combining small and easy to control systems into articulated robots capable of adapting to many scenarios. Chain structured systems are designed for

Fig. 1. On top, the representation of the hybrid platform: the main mobile base and two crawlers. On bottom, the first crawler prototype. From left to right: back module; central module; front module; docking module. The robot performs inspections in confined spaces. In challenging conditions, the vehicle connects with its twin or with the mobile base.

search and rescue or exploration missions which are similar to inspection scenarios, see for example [10].

II. CRAWLER DESCRIPTION

In this paper, the idea is to exploit modularity and self-reconfigurability to design a versatile multi-purpose hybrid platform which will consist of three systems: a mobile main base and two twins vehicles, as shown in Fig. 1. These units can perform inspections independently or in collaboration. The two vehicles are suitable for inspection in confined and constrained environments. The mobile base is more useful in patrolling wide areas. If the inspection area is too big or challenging for single units, the systems can reconfigure autonomously without human intervention. All the possible configurations of such system are described in [11], [12]. This work focuses on the design features of the vehicles and their ground maneuverability.

The vehicle consists of three main modules plus the docking module, see Fig. 1. Each module is connected with the others through active joints. The tracks on the longest modules

Fig. 2. Pictures of the crawler during experiments: a) the vehicle moving over a 0.5m ditch; b) the vehicle adopting C-configuration for turning; c) the vehicle adopting S-configuration for turning; d) the vehicle climbing a 20° slope; e) the vehicle moving on uneven terrain.

are active, while the others are passive. The tracks have a slender layout which helps in overcoming debris stuck between modules. The docking module allows autonomous mechanical coupling between two vehicles or with the base. Therefore, the docking module has a different track layout. Single DC motor concurrently drives the tracks of each active module. The drive system, which transfers motion to the tracks, is enclosed in the module chassis, to prevent damages due to debris and potential transmission failures. The system results redundant either in kinematics and actuation. Therefore, the vehicle adapts to a variety of terrains and obstacles, with a good fault-tolerance and reliability. The robot is powered through an umbilical cable which provides electrical power and control signals.

III. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

The crawler performance and its maneuverability are evaluated experimentally in common scenarios that can be met during inspection, see Fig. 2.

As first test, the vehicle performs forward/backward motion on flat terrain, achieving a speed of about 0.1m/s. As in Fig. 2(a), the crawler succeeds also in moving over 0.5m ditch, which is longer than each module length. For turning, the vehicle can use two techniques: the C-configuration and the S-configuration. In C-configuration, Fig. 2(b), the tracks spin in the same direction and the crawler rotates of about 90 degrees in 20 seconds. In S-configuration, Fig. 2(c), the tracks spin in opposite directions and the vehicle rotates of ± 90 degrees in 32 seconds. The robot can climb ramps up to 20 degrees with a reduced speed, Fig. 2(d). The crawler successfully moves on uneven terrains, Fig. 2(e). Here, all the pitch joints are disengaged, in this way, the modules adapt to the terrain and the robot traverses the 2m long terrain. If the vehicle gets stuck it is possible to rotate the modules and recover.

IV. CONCLUSION

Inspection robotics is a very active field of research. Most of the inspection operations consist in reaching target, collecting data from sensors and providing visual feedback to the operator. Still, the lack in adaptability and versatility limits the use of inspection robots in real-case scenarios.

In this paper, we propose a novel modular hybrid platform for inspection which exploits self-reconfigurability and modularity for adapting to many inspection missions. The platform consists in two modular vehicles and a mobile main base. Here, we describe the most important features of the crawler prototype. The vehicle ground maneuverability results

are reported and discussed. The robot achieves a forward velocity of 0.1m/s on flat terrain. Thanks to its structure, the crawler successfully overcomes gaps longer than its modules. The vehicle performs turning motion in C-configuration and S-configuration. Moreover, the system is tested in climbing slopes up to 20 degrees and in moving over uneven terrain. During experiments, some minor issues were identified, such as low friction on tracks, and will be addressed in future works. Future works will focus also on testing the entire crawler kinematics evaluating the spatial maneuverability of the system. Next steps will also involve the experiments on the two vehicles in snake configuration. Finally, the design of the mobile main base will be finalized and the hybrid platform performance will be evaluated.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Caprari *et al.*, "Highly compact robots for inspection of power plants," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 29, pp. 47–68, Gen. 2012.
- [2] A. Pistone *et al.*, "Reconfigurable inspection robot for industrial applications," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 38, pp. 597 – 604, 2019.
- [3] J. Steele *et al.*, "Development of an Oil and Gas Refinery Inspection Robot," *ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition, Proceedings (IMECE)*, vol. 4, pp. 1–10, Nov. 2014.
- [4] S. Soldan, J. Welle, T. Barz, A. Kroll, and D. Schulz, *Towards Autonomous Robotic Systems for Remote Gas Leak Detection and Localization in Industrial Environments*. Springer Tracts in Advanced Robotics, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, Jan. 2014, pp. 233–247, in Yoshida, K. and Tadokoro, S., *Field and Service Robotics*, ISBN: 978-3-642-40685-0.
- [5] J. Mirats-Tur and W. Garthwaite, "Robotic Devices for Water Main In-Pipe Inspection: A Survey," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 27, pp. 491–508, Jul. 2010.
- [6] G. Mills, A. Jackson, and R. Richardson, "Advances in the Inspection of Unpiggable Pipelines," *Robotics*, vol. 6, p. 36, Nov. 2017.
- [7] S. Hirose, "Snake-like locomotors and manipulators," *Biologically Inspired Robots*, 1993.
- [8] H. Schempf *et al.*, "Visual and nondestructive evaluation inspection of live gas mains using the Explorer™ family of pipe robots," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 27, pp. 217–249, May 2010.
- [9] S. A. Fjerdingen, P. Liljebäck, and A. A. Transeth, "A snake-like robot for internal inspection of complex pipe structures (PIKo)," in *2009 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, Oct. 2009, pp. 5665–5671.
- [10] W. Wei and T. Huilin, "Reconfigurable multi-robot system kinematic modeling and motion planning," in *2011 6th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications*, Jun. 2011, pp. 1672–1677.
- [11] S. Leggieri *et al.*, "Novel modular self-reconfigurable robot for pipe and plant inspection," in *ICAS 2020 : The Sixteenth International Conference on Autonomic and Autonomous Systems*, 2020, pp. 36–40.
- [12] S. Leggieri *et al.*, "Self-reconfigurable hybrid robot for inspection," in *2020 I-RIM Conference*. I-RIM, 2020, pp. 268–269.